

Application of Corpus Linguistics in Language Learning at School

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the possibilities of using a linguistic corpus in the educational process. To develop students' linguistic competence in English the process of using corpus and characteristics of the linguistic corpus are presented. The criteria for selecting texts for the linguistic corpus are analyzed and the characteristics it possesses are indicated. The conditions that must be taken into account for using the corpus in the educational process are explained.

Keywords: corpus, National Corpus, linguistic corpus, critical and creative thinking, linguistic competence, education.

INTRODUCTION

Informatization processes significantly change and make our lives easier. Information is becoming the most important resource in modern society. Preservation, enhancement and rational use of this resource has become of great importance for society.

More and more information that we use in everyday life comes in electronic format; moreover, traditional printed publications, works of literature that have become classics and priceless museum manuscripts are translated into information format. This form of information presentation allows you to organize work and access to it at a completely different quality level.

Ensuring public access of users to electronic information resources has become one of the primary tasks of information services for science, education and culture. The current information service system allows us to gain access to almost any information in unlimited quantities. A huge role in this is played by the

Internet system, which since 1991 has managed to turn into a unique and practically inexhaustible information environment.

With the advent of the Internet, a fundamentally new situation was created in the education system. The possibilities of the network for the purposes of education and personal development are truly unique. The information potential of the Internet is simply inexhaustible. The use of Internet resources allows you to diversify the educational process, as well as organize it taking into account the interests of students and their level of preparation. The century requires fundamentally new approaches to education. Education should be developmental in terms of developing independent critical and creative thinking. But for this, it is not enough to have in the education system only a teacher and a textbook (understood in a broad sense as a system of teaching aids), reflecting one point of view accepted in society. A wide information field of activity is needed; various sources of information, different views, points of view on the same problem, encouraging the student to think independently and search for his own reasoned position.

DISCUSSIONS

On the Internet, resources of various sizes are used for educational purposes - from web pages with interesting educational materials to voluminous projects. One of these large projects is the National Corpus. The development, creation and use of linguistic corpora are dealt with by such a branch of linguistics as corpus linguistics. The National Corpus is an information and reference system based on a collection of texts in electronic form. It can be used by anyone, but primarily it is designed for those who are engaged in linguistic research, study or teach the English language. A good scientific apparatus (usually called marking, or annotation, of a corpus) allows you to quickly and efficiently find in texts examples of words, forms and structures that interest the user.

One of the main functions of a corpus in teaching the English language is to serve as a source of examples. The corpus can provide invaluable assistance to teachers in finding language material for compiling individual, control and test tasks on vocabulary, morphology, and syntax.

V.A. Plungyan states: “The use of the Corpus in teaching humanities at school will help to successfully solve both purely scientific and pedagogical problems” [1, p. 12].

N.R. Dobrushin and A.I. Levinson considers three main areas for using the Corpus:

- .Compilation of tasks and exercises.
- . Organization of independent research work of students and schoolchildren.
- . Verification of data from dictionaries and textbooks.

Electronic libraries are also becoming widespread in the educational process. The advantages of the electronic form of the document compared to the printed one are the reliability and compactness of information storage, the possibility of its rapid distribution and widespread use.

The electronic library facilitates the following main functions:

- . Information, aimed at satisfying the need for information of various categories of users in all branches of knowledge or one of the subject areas.
- . Educational, implemented, including through the popularization of electronic documents related to history and culture.
- . Research, focused on promoting in-depth study of a topic (subject) by scientists and specialists.
- . Educational, within which support is provided for both basic and additional education by providing not only multimedia educational material, but also the necessary literature.
- . A reference service that allows you to obtain reliable information reflected in documents of a certain type.

Thus, a teacher, using the Internet system, can:

- a) update the material in your own textbooks;
- b) find additional information;
- c) develop training materials;
- d) post educational information.

Thus, the subject of corpus linguistics is “the theoretical foundations and practical mechanisms for the creation and use of representative arrays of language data intended for linguistic research in the interests of a wide range of users” [3, p. 5]. The British National Corpus (BNC) is a widely accepted model. Many other modern buildings are oriented towards it. The national corpus has two important features.

Firstly, it is characterized by representativeness, or a balanced composition of texts. This means that the corpus contains, if possible, all types of written and oral texts presented in a given language (fiction of different genres, journalistic, educational, scientific, business, colloquial, dialect, etc.), and that all of the above texts are included in the corpus if possible, in proportion to their share in the language of the corresponding period. It should be borne in mind that good representativeness is achieved only with a significant volume of the corpus (tens and hundreds of millions of word uses).

Secondly, the corpus contains special additional information about the properties of the texts included in it (the so-called markup, or annotation). Marking is the main characteristic of the case. It distinguishes a corpus from the simple collections (or “libraries”) of texts that abound on the Internet. For the compilers of the National Corpus, factors such as the fascination or usefulness of a book, its high artistic or scientific merits are important, but not paramount. The national corpus, unlike an electronic library, is not a collection of “interesting” or “useful” texts for language learning. And these could be, along with classic works of

fiction, a novel by a minor writer, a recording of an ordinary telephone conversation, a standard rental agreement, etc.

The linguistic corpus was first created in the 1960s at Brown University (USA) on computer media. W. Francis and G. Kucera designed it as a set of five hundred two thousand word prose printed texts of American English. The texts belonged to the fifteen most popular genres of English-language printed prose in the United States. One of the authors, W. Francis, used the word “corpus” to mean “a body of texts considered representative of a given language, dialect or other subset of a language, intended for linguistic analysis.” The appearance of the Brown Linguistic Corpus in 1963 aroused widespread interest and lively debate. First of all, they touched upon the principles of text selection and the composition of problems potentially solved using this corpus. W. Francis and G. Kucera aimed to present a corpus of texts that meet clear and precise selection criteria:

1. Origin and composition of the text (the author had to be a native speaker of American English, the dialogue had to occupy less than half the volume of the text).
2. Synchronization (texts were included).
3. A thoughtful relationship between the numerical representation of various genres and the selection of individual texts using a special probabilistic procedure.
4. Availability for computer processing (special marks for conveying graphic features of the text, etc.)

This is how the concept of “linguistic corpus” was born. In corpus linguistics, the definition of a corpus is based on four features. These main substantive features that determine the specificity of this unique kind of verbal unity are:

- 1) location of the case on machine media (machine readable form);
- 2) a standardized presentation of verbal material on this computer medium, allowing the use of standard programs for its processing and sampling procedures;
- 3) final size (design criteria);

4) representativeness (representativeness is the name of the set of principles or requirements on the basis of which the corpus was organized or compiled).

Currently, there are many linguistic corpora on the Internet, which are classified by genre, industry, and language. They can be used in the educational process, for example, American National Corpus (ANC), The British National Corpus (BNC), The Reuters Corpus, The Bank of English, English Internet Corpus) [5].

In accordance with the selected features possessed by linguistic corpora, V.V. Rykov [8] concludes that the first three characteristics (machine readable form, sampling, design criteria) define a certain set of texts located on machine media and presented in a form convenient for software processing. The last feature (representativeness), which defines a corpus, is a sign of representativeness. The corpus must present the diversity of the phenomenon being studied with maximum objectivity and at the same time give an objective picture of the application of this phenomenon in the speech practice of a native speaker [8].

It is this property of the linguistic corpus that can and should be used in the educational process when teaching vocabulary at the senior level.

MATERIALS AND ANALYSIS

The corpus has proven particularly useful for refining current descriptions of language features and for contextualizing language use. There are many types of corpora, and applications of these corpora can be found in many different areas of research.

This type of corpus is designed to include a wide selection of all registers and genres of a given language. The Brown Corpus and the LOB Corpus are the first reference corpora for American and British English, respectively, although they are very small by current standards, neither of which contains spoken language. A modern corpus is BNC, at least 100 million words or more, and is often divided into subcorpora available for smaller or more specialized studies.

Language corpora are divided into several corpora according to their purpose and content. There are general, special, written and oral, comparative, parallel, monitor types. Based on scientific sources, we study and analyze the main types of corpus types in language teaching and learning.

In turn, corpora differ according to their goals and tasks, and on the types of corpora used in language teaching and learning, Scientists such as E. Friginal, A. O'Keffee, I. Timmes, J. Bennit, D. Liu conducted research on this issues.

When we analyzed the works of corpus scientists who revealed the content and essence of corpus types, we realized that the types of corpus used in language teaching differ from each other. A. O'Keffee divided corpus types into three groups, i.e. monolingual, comparative, parallel corpuses. That is, monolingual corpora are a collection of texts related to only one language, consisting of sources provided in one language. Comparative corpora contain texts compiled from two or more languages. A parallel corpus is one corpus in a set of two or more monolingual corpuses, usually each in a different language, built according to the same principles. Therefore, the content is similar and the results are comparable between corpora, even though they are not translations of each other, and when users search these corpora, they can use the same metadata in the corpora.

In the book "Corpus Linguistics for ELT" by I. Timmes pointed out that three types are important in teaching English, and distinguished general, learning and pedagogical types of corpus with examples. The most common of these three types is the general case.

The American corpus scientist G. Bennit divided corpus types into generalized, special, educational, pedagogical, historical, parallel, comparative and monitor corpuses. These types of corpus differ according to the purpose, and the main 4 types are general, special, learning, and pedagogical types, which are useful for classes. BNC, COCA dictionaries are used as oral and written resources in general for language teaching purposes.

The Chinese scientist D. Liu distinguished four types of the main categories of the corpus and their categorization according to the purpose and content of education. As a result, it is divided into generalized, special, learning, parallel corpora, which are important for language teaching and learning. However, we do not agree with the recommendations regarding the use of parallel corpora in language teaching among these types, because parallel corpora may cause difficulties in learning two languages through corpora. The corpus includes speech skills of reading, writing, listening, speaking, lexical and grammatical skills, linguistic skills for elementary and advanced learners; is used as language material in the development of polysemy, synonyms, homonyms, etc.

English scientist M. Barlow said that "the corpus can reveal not only the range of language units that the student should learn, but also the frequency of their use, which is an important factor in creating curricula and language materials. In addition, the use of corpora can fundamentally change second language learning and linguistics.

CONCLUSIONS

Thus, according to the above opinion, textbooks created on the basis of corpus in language learning give examples that are often found in real life. Corpus-based learning materials, with their reliability and validity, ensure that learners are more motivated to learn the language.

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